

Cahow or Bermuda Petrel
(Pterodroma cahow)

**5-Year Status Review:
Summary and Evaluation**

Immature Cahow

photo by Jeremy Madeiros, Bermuda Department of Environment and Natural Resources

U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
Southeast Region
Raleigh Ecological Services Field Office
Raleigh, NC
November 2024

5-YEAR STATUS REVIEW
Cahow or Bermuda Petrel (*Pterodroma cahow*)

GENERAL INFORMATION

Current Classification: Endangered

Lead Field Office: Raleigh Ecological Services Field Office

Review Author: Dale Suiter, Raleigh Ecological Services Field Office, (984) 308-0971

Reviewers:

Lead Regional Office: Southeast Region, Carrie Straight

Cooperating Field Office(s):

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Maine Ecological Services Field Office, Juliana Berube

Cooperating Regional Office(s): Northeast Region, Martin Miller

Date of original listing: June 2, 1970 (35 FR 8491; June 2, 1970)

Methodology used to complete the review:

In accordance with section 4(c)(2) of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (Act), the purpose of a status review is to assess each threatened species or endangered species to determine whether its status has changed and if it should be classified differently or removed from the Lists of Threatened and Endangered Wildlife and Plants ([50 CFR 424.11](#)). The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) evaluated the best available information about the cahow's biology, habitat, and threats to inform this status review.

We announced initiation of this review in the Federal Register on May 11, 2023 (88 FR 30324) with a 60-day comment period and we received no comments. The primary sources of information used in this analysis were Bermuda's recovery plan (Madeiros 2005), peer-reviewed reports, agency reports (Madeiros 2021), unpublished survey data and reports, and personal communication with recognized experts. This review was completed by the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Raleigh Ecological Services Field Office, Raleigh, North Carolina. All literature and documents used for this review are on file at the Field Office. All comments received were evaluated and incorporated into this final document as appropriate. All recommendations resulting from this review are the result of thoroughly reviewing the best available information on the cahow.

FR Notice citation announcing the species is under active review:
May 11, 2023 (88 FR 30324)

Species' Recovery Priority Number at start of 5-year review ([48 FR 43098](#)):

1 (a monotypic species with high degree of threat and recovery potential). This species is not a monotypic species in the genus *Pterodroma*, so we have changed the Recovery Priority Number. See the Results/Signatures sections at the end of this document for the updated priority number.

Review History:

Previous 5-year reviews recommending no change in status were published on August 20, 2019, and October 30, 2013 (Service 2013, Service 2019).

REVIEW ANALYSIS

Listed Entity

Taxonomy and nomenclature

We are not aware of any changes to the taxonomy of this entity, and it is still considered valid by the Service.

Distinct Population Segment (DPS) ([61 FR 4722](#))

The Act defines species as including any subspecies of fish or wildlife or plants, and any distinct population segment of any species of vertebrate wildlife. This species was not listed as a DPS, and we have no new information that would indicate the species should be listed as a DPS under the Service's 1996 DPS Policy.

Recovery Criteria

Recovery Plan or Outline

The only known land habitat for the cahow is located in Bermuda. The Government of Bermuda developed a recovery plan with objective, measurable criteria for the cahow (Madeiros 2005). The cahow does not have a final, approved recovery plan.

Biology and Habitat Summary

The cahow is a nocturnal ground-nesting seabird, which is only known to nest on six tiny islets in Bermuda (Figure 1). It is one of the world's rarest seabirds. The breeding season for this species begins in late October and ends in mid-June (Wingate 1973). Females lay a single egg in January. Eggs hatch in February or early March and young birds fledge in late May to early June (Murphy and Mowbray 1951, Wingate 1978). A large number of artificial burrows supplement the small number of natural nest sites that meet the requirements of the cahow. Approximately 80 percent of cahow nesting pairs use artificial burrows (Carlile et al. 2012).

FIGURE 1. Map of the Nesting Islands of Bermuda petrel (cahow) (*Pterodroma cahow*). Prepared by the Terrestrial Conservation Division Office, Department of Environment and Natural Resources, Bermuda.

According to Madeiros (2021), the 2020-2021 cahow nesting season had 143 breeding pairs that produced 71 fledged chicks. This represents a breeding success rate of 49.25 percent, which was down from a record high of 55.7 percent recorded in 2019. The greatest number of fledged chicks was 73 in 2019 (Madeiros 2019). The estimated total population at the end of the 2024 nesting season was 425 to 450 birds which includes 330 breeding adults (165 breeding pairs), 72 fledglings plus an unknown number of nonbreeding adults/immature birds) (J. Madeiros pers. comm. 2024). The annual number of breeding pairs and reproductive success from 1962 to 2023 is summarized in figure 2.

**NUMBER OF BREEDING PAIRS AND REPRODUCTIVE SUCCESS OF THE CAHOW
(1962 – 2023)**

FIGURE 2. Total number of cahow breeding pairs and young fledged between 1962 and 2023. Graph generated using data from Bermuda’s breeding reports and papers (J. Madeiros, pers. comm. 2024, K. Sutherland pers. comm. 2024).

The cahow recovery project has been establishing new nesting colonies on larger islands that are more elevated and therefore at less risk from flooding, erosion, and sea level rise than the original small nesting islets. In 2004, biologists began to move young birds to the new nesting colonies prior to fledging so they could imprint on the new burrow and nesting area. The overall number of breeding pairs nesting in the new colonies has continued to grow. During the 2020-2021 breeding season, a total of 28 pairs nested in the new nesting colonies on Nonsuch Island. Between 2009 and 2021, a total of 102 chicks have fledged from new nesting colonies created on Nonsuch Island (Madeiros 2021).

Adult cahows forage over an area stretching from the east coast of North America (both U.S. and Canada) to western European waters (Madeiros 2012, Raine et al. 2021). A recent study by Raine et al. (2021) tracked five birds that were tagged at the nesting grounds in Bermuda. They observed birds taking short and long foraging excursions. During short trips (approximately 1 day in duration), they typically remained within Bermudian waters. Long trips (greater than 4 days in duration) made up nearly 98 percent of their time at sea, and the birds traveled far beyond Bermudian territorial waters to areas offshore of the mid-Atlantic and New England states and northeastern Canadian provinces and east to western European waters. The Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF, 2021) includes observations in waters of North Carolina and South Carolina. On a pelagic birding trip, the Brookline Bird Club observed one in the vicinity of the Northeast Canyons and Seamounts Marine National Monument southeast of Cape Cod, Massachusetts (Bonomo 2019).

According to a recent genetic study by Alfonso et al. (2023), the cahow suffered a recent genetic bottleneck and shows low mitochondrial diversity compared with other petrel species. While

they found some highly inbred individuals, they determined that inbreeding levels were not high overall.

We are not aware of any additional new biology or habitat information since the most recent species review that impacts the status of the species, and all of the information provided in the last 5-year review remains valid (Service 2013, Service 2019).

Threats (Five-Factor Analysis) Summary

The status of a species is determined from an assessment of factors specified in section 4 (a)(1) of the Act. A summary of this assessment is detailed below.

Factor A: the present or threatened destruction, modification, or curtailment of its habitat or range.

As mentioned in the 2013 5-year review (Service 2013), flooding from hurricanes, storms, and sea level rise have damaged the nesting islets in Bermuda and continue to threaten this species. In 2020, three significant hurricanes caused considerable flooding and damage to cahow nesting islets. Approximately two-thirds of the concrete nest burrows used by the cahow were made unusable by the floodwaters (Madeiros 2021). Climate change models predict the intensity of tropical storms to increase in the coming years (Knutson 2022). It is likely that flooding will cause some of the nesting cavities to become unusable within a few years, which could reduce the number of fledglings (K. Sutherland, pers. comm., June 19, 2024). Madeiros (2021) listed insufficient safe nesting habitat and suitable deep nest burrows or rock crevices as a threat to the species. The Bermuda Department of Conservation Services' recovery program is working to expand cahow nesting habitat by creating artificial burrows in higher locations that are less likely to flood. In addition to changes in nesting habitat, offshore wind has the potential to change foraging habitat and although the impacts are unknown. Offshore wind structures have the potential to impact foraging behavior and movements and could result in direct mortality from collisions with structures at sea (Desholm and Kahlert 2005; Ramos et al. 2017).

Factor B: overutilization for commercial, recreational, scientific, or educational purposes.

The cahow was historically hunted nearly to extinction by early colonists. Now the national bird of Bermuda, the Bermuda petrel is protected on the island. We have no indication that overutilization for commercial, recreational, scientific, or educational purposes is currently a threat to this species.

Factor C: disease or predation.

As described in the 2013 5-year review, introduced mammals such as pigs, dogs, cats, and rats, and native species, such as peregrine falcons and snowy owls, have been observed preying on cahow chicks (Service 2013). We believe these are likely still threats to the species. Madeiros (2021) noted that predation from rats that swim from mainland Bermuda to nesting islands remains a threat to the species. In addition, the cahow may suffer from nest-site competition from the native longtail or white-tailed tropicbirds (*Phaethon lepturus catsbyii*), which nest in similar habitat (Madeiros 2021).

Factor D: the inadequacy of existing regulatory mechanisms.

The 2013 5-year review has a detailed summary of U.S., Bermuda, and United Kingdom laws that protect this species (Service 2013). Although protections are in place for the known nesting locations in Bermuda, those protections are limited in their reduction of some of these threats, and there are limited protections for the species throughout its foraging range (when at sea).

Factor E: other natural or manmade factors affecting its continued existence.

Several human induced threats may have negative effects on this species. Human disturbance through illegal landings on the nesting islets and vandalism to the nest burrows may be harmful to the species (Madeiros 2021). Light pollution from the main islands of Bermuda, especially the airport can disrupt courtship activity and nighttime fledging of the chicks in this nocturnal species (Madeiros 2021). According to Robinson-Willmott et al. (2013), the cahow may be very sensitive to Offshore Wind Energy Infrastructure projects located on the Atlantic Outer Continental Shelf. The development of offshore wind and oil/gas reserves in the eastern United States and Canada may also pose a threat to this pelagic species during long foraging flights (see above; Raine et al. 2021). Although it has not been evaluated for Bermuda petrel, as seen in other ocean-foraging birds, there is potential for collisions with shipping traffic and mortality as bycatch in commercial fisheries (Brothers et al. 2010; Satgé et al. 2023; Zhou et al. 2019).

Climate. As discussed under Factor A, changes in climate are currently impacting the species through flooding of burrows and nesting areas from sea level rise and storm surges.

Plastics. Plastic ingestion is another potential threat mentioned in the 2019 5-year review (Service 2019). Microplastics (10-1000 µm) are found in high levels in the Atlantic Ocean (Pabortsava and Lampitt 2020) and recent studies have shown that “microplastics were associated with decreases in commensal microbiota and increases in (zoonotic) pathogens and antibiotic-resistant and plastic-degrading microbes” (Fackelmann et al. 2023). We are unaware of the level of microplastic ingestion of this species, but it remains a concern that needs future assessment.

Toxic chemicals. Since the previous 5-year review, scientists evaluated blood and feather samples for the presence of Persistent Organic Pesticides (POPs) in cahows. Three Organochlorinated pesticides (OCPs) were found in cahows. Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethylene (DDE) was confirmed in 100 percent of sampled cahows and Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT) was confirmed in the blood samples of less than 30 percent of the sampled cahows. These two pesticides affect calcium uptake in various bird species resulting in thin eggshells which are more easily broken during incubation, thus reducing survival (Madeiros 2021). The carcinogen hexachlorobenzene (HCB) was detected in more than 50 percent of sampled cahows (Madeiros 2021). An additional study examined OCP, polychlorinated biphenyl ether (PCB), polybrominated diphenyl ether (PBDE), and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) exposure of breeding cahows. A wide range of contaminants were found in sub-lethal doses, with PCBs dominant; found in 60% of individuals sampled (Campioni et al, 2024). All of these chemicals have a potential to reduce nesting success through decreased eggshell thickness and/or compromised health of reproductive adults. Campioni et al (2024) confirmed that females with greater contaminant burdens (particularly PCBs) laid eggs with a lower probability of hatching.

Synthesis

The cahow is a nocturnal, ground-nesting seabird that is only known to nest on six tiny islets in Bermuda. The 2020-2021 cahow nesting season had a record high of 143 breeding pairs that fledged 71 chicks. This represents a breeding success rate of 49.25 percent which is slightly lower than the highest breeding success rate of 55.7 percent in 2019 when 73 chicks were fledged. The annual number of breeding pairs and reproductive success increased gradually from 1962 to 2005 and increased precipitously between 2005 and 2023. The 2024 estimated total population is 425 to 450 birds, including 165 breeding pairs and 72 fledglings. The cahow is highly threatened by flooding from hurricanes, storms, and sea level rise which may damage or destroy the only nesting areas for this species. Climate change is expected to cause more intense tropical storms and exacerbate coastal flooding which threatens successful reproduction. Cahows also compete for the limited remaining nesting habitat with another native pelagic bird, the longtail. Non-native species, especially rats, are a threat to nesting adults, eggs, and chicks. Toxic chemicals, including three pesticides, have been found in cahows, one of which has been associated with reduced probability of hatching and the other two may affect calcium uptake resulting in thin eggshells making them more at risk to breaking during the incubation period. Another detected pesticide is a known carcinogen. Human disturbances such as illegal landings on nesting islets, light pollution, plastic ingestion, and the development of offshore wind and oil/gas reserves in the eastern United States and Canada may also threaten this species. Because of ongoing threats and the current condition of the species, the cahow continues to meet the definition of an endangered species.

RECOMMENDED FUTURE ACTIVITIES

The 2013 and 2019 5-year reviews for this species included a detailed discussion of recommended actions that will contribute to the recovery of this species (Service 2013, Service 2019). Since nesting occurs only in Bermuda and the species spends a large part of its life at sea, implementation of these recovery actions is difficult and little progress has been made. These actions remain important to the long-term survival of the species. No additional recovery activities were identified during the course of this status review. As offshore wind development increases throughout the range of Bermuda petrel and other petrel species, we emphasize the recommended activities from the 2019 5-year review assessing the impact of structures and associated activities on Bermuda petrel.

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RESULTS / SIGNATURES

U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service Status Review of Cahow or Bermuda Petrel

Status Recommendation:

On the basis of this review, we recommend the following status for this species. A 5-year review presents a recommendation of the species status. Any change to the status requires a separate rulemaking process that includes public review and comment, as defined in the Act.

Downlist to Threatened

Uplist to Endangered

Delist:

The species is extinct

The species does not meet the definition of an endangered or threatened species

The species is recovered.

New information indicates the species does not meet the definition of an endangered or threatened species.

The listed entity does not meet the statutory definition of a species.

No change needed

New Recovery Priority Number ([48 FR 43098](#)):

The cahow (*Pterodroma cahow*) is a member of the Genus *Pterodroma*, which includes approximately 35 species, therefore it is not considered a monotypic species (i.e., the only species in the genus) (Winkler et al. 2020). Based on this review, we still believe the species has a high degree of threat and a high recovery potential, so we recommend a new Recovery Priority Number of 2 to indicate a correction from monotypic species to species.

FIELD OFFICE APPROVAL:

Field Supervisor (Acting), Raleigh Ecological Services Field Office, Fish and Wildlife Service

Approve _____

COOPERATING REGIONAL OFFICE APPROVAL:

We emailed this 5-year review to the Northeast Regional Office for their concurrence prior to finalizing the document. We will retain any comments that we received, as well as verification of concurrence from other regions, in the administrative record for this 5-year review.